

THIS IS AN IMPORTANT MESSAGE FOR JULIE WADE: EMERGENT PERFORMANCE EVENTS IN AN INTERACTIVE INSTALLATION

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ABSTRACT

This is an important message for Julie Wade exists both as a multimedia performance piece and as an interactive audiovisual installation. Each version of the work was publicly presented between 2013 and 2015; a recent 2016 version seeks to incorporate elements of both of the earlier performance and installation versions. Currently, the work may be installed in a gallery space and controlled by Max/Jitter patches that randomly generate related audio and visual events; at the same time, this new installation remains open to interactive musical performance, responding to such interventions with extra layers of sound and revealing an extra set of video clips. This hybrid environment raises a number of ontological questions. In what ways are these musical interactions with the installation “performances”? Is a musician interacting with the installation a “performer” in the conventional sense, and does this interaction impose a different role on a casual gallery visitor witnessing this interaction? Can this mode of presentation of an audiovisual work transcend the limitations of conventional performance and installation? This paper explores these questions within the context of the evolution and 2016 presentation of *This is an important message for Julie Wade*.

1. INTRODUCTION

This is an important message for Julie Wade is an audiovisual piece created from found sound and dozens of video clips gathered over a period of ten years. The process of developing *This is an important message for Julie Wade* began in 2002 with a series of automated phone messages intended for a woman named Julie Wade who presumably had been associated with the phone number assigned to us when we moved to our new city. The calls invariably began with a male voice saying, “This is an important message for...” followed by another male voice saying “Julie Wade”. The message would continue, requesting that Julie Wade contact a certain phone number and quote a certain file number. For many months I simply deleted the messages as they came in, but when the messages starting to vary in subtle ways (different

voices, different texts), I began saving them with the idea of eventually using the messages as source material for some sort of sound art piece.

The first version of the work was presented as an audiovisual installation in 2013; ten years of phone messages were edited into multiple tracks of audio, some of which only include the recitation of the phone and file numbers. These audio tracks are randomly accessed through a Max algorithm and dispersed through four channels to loudspeakers surrounding the installation space. Black and white video projected on one wall of the gallery features a noisy and indistinct image occasionally interrupted by short video clips of numbers gathered from road signs, advertisements, and building addresses. An additional background layer of audio was created from heavily processing the sound of the ringing telephone to create a murky and dense sonic texture. The installed work has an interesting effect, as it juxtaposes the cheerful tone of the text recitations, the anxiety related to repeated messages from a collection agency, and the multiple levels of randomness reflected in the origins and the treatment of the audiovisual material.

The following year I developed a performance version of *Julie Wade* for inclusion in a program of multimedia performance pieces. In the performance version, the sound of a live instrumentalist is used to trigger an additional set of video clips featuring a woman sitting in a room, ostensibly Julie Wade herself waiting for a phone call. The musician improvises unusual sounds on their instrument (squeals, thick dissonances, multi-phonics, blurred flurries of notes, etc.); the modified Max algorithm brings up one of the Julie Wade video clips with each new live sonic gesture. The performance version is framed by the playback of contrasting but complete and unaltered phone messages, and has been performed and well-received multiple times.

2. PERFORMANCES, INSTALLATIONS, AND INTERACTIVITY

A performance is, among other things, a unique event in a specific time frame, usually with more or less clear beginning and end points.¹ With most performances, these

¹ An action within a time frame is one of multiple features (contestably) intrinsic to performances across cultures and artistic disciplines. For a more in depth discussion of the nature of performance see Carlson [1].

points are equally understood by the performers and the viewing audience, and are conventionally marked by ritual actions such as the entry of a performer onto a stage or the applause offered by the audience² at the end of the performance. Over time these conventions have been challenged in any number of ways, such as beginning a performance surreptitiously or by surprise, requiring voluntary or involuntary audience participation, dispersing performers into space normally reserved for the audience, or presenting very long performances that invite the audience to come and go as they please. Still, the drama and significance of such challenges to convention are often premised on the audience's expectation of the rituals that surround performance events.

Installation works also reflect on some level a similar consideration of a set of conventions and rituals. Anne Ring Peterson suggests that installations share three fundamental characteristics: 1) that they activate "space and context", 2) that they stretch an artistic work in time, and 3) that they focus on the "viewer's bodily and subjective experience" [2]. A performance within an installation by its nature addresses its situation in three-dimensional space as well as the expected behaviour of those experiencing the work. While the physical boundaries of the installation space may be generally understood by gallery visitors, the timeframes within which visitors experience an installation differ widely and are not likely to be coordinated. As with performances, rituals of participation apply, though they tend to be the rituals of the art gallery: visitors navigating the installation for a few moments before proceeding to the next gallery space, or perhaps experiencing the installation in the context of an opening, with a glass of wine and friendly chat. The characterization of performances as distinctly temporal and installations as distinctly spatial is not new,³ but does carry implications for the way a work is experienced: audience members share an experience in a given time, while gallery visitors share an experience in a given space.⁴

Interactive is a term that is often applied to varieties of both performances and installations. For musicians and dancers, *interactive* usually describes a relationship between the performer and the work, while within installations and other genres rooted in a visual arts tradition,

interactive describes a relationship between the viewing audience and the work. This distinction becomes important when broadly considering the nature of interaction in interactive audiovisual installations. The use of microphones, cameras, sensors and software to capture data representing sound and movement creates the interactive interface between the work and the individuals in the installation space.⁵ But the level of complexity and sophistication of sound and movement generated by trained artists exceeds the level that can be expected of a general public, and thus an interactive installation that requires training and preparation of its "performers" presents another world of artistic possibilities, a world that exists in all of the performing arts.

3. THIS IS AN IMPORTANT MESSAGE FOR JULIE WADE

In what ways are musical interactions with an installation "performances"? Is a musician interacting with the installation a "performer" in the conventional sense, and does this interaction impose a different role on a casual gallery visitor witnessing this interaction? The multiple versions of the *Julie Wade* piece have created an opportunity to isolate these questions and examine them from different perspectives.

In the original installation version of *Julie Wade* there is no performer; a Max algorithm controls the playback of audio and video clips while gallery visitors come and go as they please. This first version isn't interactive at all (perhaps *generative* would be a better work to describe it), though the idea of feeding a signal from a microphone into the Max patch to trigger the extra layer of video and reveal the waiting Julie Wade emerged from the process of working on the early installation version. This idea was implemented in the "performance version" of the piece, where a series of saxophone multi-phonics that blend well with the other sonic elements is used as the interactive trigger. Based on a simple patch that measured amplitude changes to trigger the extra video clips, it was easy to in turn incorporate that element into the installation version with the idea that visitors could trigger the extra video clips with any sound that was loud enough (clapping, finger-snapping, etc.).

Distinctions between the two versions emerged. The use of a musical instrument in itself suggested "performance", even as the piece developed. Finger-snapping was an integral part of testing the patch, but testing the patch with the saxophone gestures felt more like *rehearsing* than *testing*. The possibility of taking turns at the microphone to trigger the video clips exists in the installation version, but the performance version restricts the triggering to a designated instrumentalist. Taking turns confers no special status on anyone interacting with the

² I am using the term *audience* for listeners in a concert performance situation, *viewing audience* for those attending a dance or theatre performance, and *gallery visitors* for people experiencing an installation. I use the term *performer* in all situations, even though the term is not quite right for even the hybrid installation context. These choices remain difficult, as the terms connote different levels of passive or active participation, and in themselves confer roles on individuals that the work is in part designed to question. This issue of terminology is central to audience studies, and has been explored by numerous scholars. The 2010 issue of the journal *About Performance* is devoted to audience studies, and several of the essays included therein address the implications of terminology; Laura Ginters' introductory article offers an overview of recent research focusing on audiences, spectators, and their roles [3].

³ Gascia Ouzounian's dissertation on sound art and spatial installations thoroughly explores this idea, positing different varieties of spaces within which installations can be situated [4].

⁴ Of course performances still take place in space and installations are still experienced over time; without oversimplifying, the practices and rituals that inform performances and installations differ in part in their temporal and spatial considerations.

⁵ David Saltz distinguishes between interactive computer art in which interactivity is a feature of a performance and art in which the interactivity constitutes an environment. In the former case, the interaction still produces performances that are tokens of a "work", be that work a play, a musical composition, a dance or a ritual. In the latter case, interaction does not produce a token of a work, but is inextricably a part of the work itself [5].

installation, but my rehearsal of the saxophone gestures and ability to create a musical shape over time put me in a position to make a performance in a way that a finger-snapping gallery visitor never could. At the first public performance of the piece in Norway in 2014, the saxophone interface in a sense produced both a performer and an audience: we accepted these roles that the situation had created for us.

Building a performance piece from the raw materials of the installation posed its own challenges. The various audio elements of the installation version became a background for the musical gestures of the live musician(s), and live processing of the audio signal coming from the musician(s) helped create a connection between the acoustic and electronic sound sources. The performance version relies to a large extent on the improvising musician(s) to create a structure in time that manages to reflect the randomness that is part of the character of the piece yet still holds the attention of an audience for several minutes. The performance version is framed by complete and unedited statements of different versions of the original phone messages that function as cues that the performance has begun and ended.

The 2016 hybrid version of *Julie Wade* combines elements of the installation and performance versions in an attempt to overcome some of the limitations of each medium. The hybrid version is realized in a three-dimensional space that denies the possibility of a “stage” area; a perpendicular projection surface created from suspended fabric dissects the space and requires the performer and gallery visitors to navigate the space in order to perceive different elements of the work. Central to this version is the idea of an emergent performance event, that is, a performance that materializes without the rituals that mark the formal beginning and ending of a performance. The installation functions as before, but the opportunity exists for an instrumentalist to interact with the installation for a few moments, triggering audio and video events that may not have appeared otherwise or that may have been left to a random process.⁶

The first realization of this version took place over several hours, with visitors coming and going as they pleased and with performance events happening periodically over that time. The improvisational “performances” were not structured to create a musical whole in a conventional sense (though a certain amount of musical structuring by the instrumentalist and listener is probably inevitable); rather, the musical gestures were relatively short, discontinuous, and unevenly spaced over time. Gallery visitors were few enough that it was possible to engage with them in brief conversation before playing the instrument and between gestures, and to consciously disallow performance conventions to establish the event as a conventional performance. Still, this hybrid environment raised a number of ontological questions. In what ways do these musical interactions with the installation remain

“performances”? Is a musician interacting with the installation remain a “performer” in the conventional sense, and does this interaction impose a different role on a casual gallery visitor witnessing this interaction? Can this mode of presentation of an audiovisual work transcend in some ways the limitations of conventional performance and installation?

photo credit: Sigi Torinus

As the creator and performer of the piece, I found the hybrid installation environment to be the most satisfying of the three versions; the unpredictability of certain aspects of the installation response made for an engaging aesthetic experience not dissimilar to improvising with other musicians, the video triggering engendered a sense of connection to the visual aspect of the installation, and the freedom to move around the space encouraged a more contemplative approach to the work. I was also pleased to hand over aspects of control of the listening experience to the gallery visitors; they could stay as long as they wished, they could be close to me or far away from me if they chose, and they could chat with each other without fear of interrupting a formal performance. Nonetheless, interacting with the installation while others in the space watched and listened seemed to ineluctably take on some aspects of a formal performance: I was privileged in that only I had access to the installation interface (in this case, the microphone), the sounds that I made for better or worse imposed themselves on the experience of others, and, perhaps in part due to the brevity of the emergent performance events, no gallery visitors left the space while I was playing. At the same time, no one applauded when I stopped playing, and gallery visitors for the most part continued to move around the space as they pleased.

The gallery visitors experienced some unease with the emergence of performance events; for some the proximity of the instrumentalist was disturbing, and responses varied from seeking a refuge on the periphery of the space to clowning with the installation. One visitor reported a discomfort with her perception that she was becoming an element of the work, in part because of the ongoing documentation taking place with multiple cameras. It was clear that the space that the audience normally inhabits in a performance had been transgressed by the instrumentalist, forcing a new and in some ways confusing role on the gallery visitors. All the same, those visitors that stayed for some length of time became accustomed to the occasional musical gestures, and within

⁶ An interesting parallel exists in the performances of dada artists in the early part of the twentieth century. The dada artists often performed with little consideration of the audience, and were more preoccupied with their own experience within the art work and with the experience of other members of their group. This idea is explored in Annabelle Melzer's extensive research relating to dada performance practices. [6]

minutes had resumed the behaviours typical of casual visitors to an art gallery.

While I had spent much time anticipating the reaction of gallery visitors to the hybrid installation experience, I was surprised to find that the situation also posed some challenges for the musician that I had not anticipated. As the musician, I found it was difficult at first to identify an appropriate attitude to take in making the musical gestures. Should I present these gestures with intensity of a musical performer, or should the gestures be made more casually with the playfulness of an engaged participant in an interactive installation? Neither intensity nor playfulness seemed to reflect the nature of the work, so I adopted an attitude of detached experimentation and tried to approximate a random choice of gestures. This seemed to work well, though it became clear that future presentations of the piece with different musicians might require some discussion of this issue as part of an orientation to the work.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Ultimately, the hybrid mode of presentation seems to hold significant potential for an enriched experience of an interactive audiovisual work, both for the improvising musician and for the gallery visitors. From a visitor's perspective, the situation is in some ways akin to watching someone with considerable skill play a sport or a video game; there is an element of performance, but the "performer" is engaged with the activity in a way that is less directed at the observers and more with the game itself. This aspect will be developed more in future work.

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